

Complexation of Salicylanilide with Some Metal Ions of Biological Interest

R. SAHAI*, S. AGRAWAL and S. S. S. KUSHWAHA

Department of Chemistry, V. S. S. D. College, Kanpur-208 002

Manuscript received 21 July 1980, revised 27 July 1981, accepted 1 May 1982

In order to examine complexation as a possible mode of action of some fungicides, the complexation of salicylanilide with a few metal ions of biological interest, such as, Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Zr(IV), La(III) and Th(IV), has been studied potentiometrically using Calvin-Bjerrum titration technique as employed by Irving and Rossotti. Protonation constant of the ligand and stability constants of the respective metal complexes have been determined at constant temperature (25°) and ionic strength (0.1 M, KNO₃) in 70% (v/v) dioxan-water medium. Complexes of salicylanilide with Fe(III), Ni(II) and Cu(II) have also been prepared and characterized on the basis of elemental analysis and ir spectral data. A possible mechanism of action of this fungicide has been discussed.

THE activity of various metal ions in biological systems has been explained on the basis of different complexed species formed in the living organisms^{1,2}. Metal ions are found in several fungi³ and are reported to play important role in different enzymatic reactions. A survey of literature reveals that the role of metal ions in fungicidal activity is rather unexplored. Salicylanilide is a potential fungicide³ and its mode of action has been investigated only to the extent of some physiological^{3,4} changes occurring in fungi but the structural features have not been considered. To explore this aspect of fungicidal activity, complexation of salicylanilide with some metal ions of biological interest, such as, Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Zr(IV), La(III) and Th(IV) has been investigated in solution potentiometrically. The complexes of Fe(III), Ni(II) and Cu(II) with salicylanilide have also been isolated in solid state and studied to establish the site of interaction.

Experimental

Materials: All the metal nitrates used were of AR grade and their solutions were prepared in carbonate free double distilled water. Salicylanilide was obtained from Fluka A.G. and weighed quantity of the anilide was dissolved in 70% (v/v) dioxan-water medium.

Potentiometric measurements: A Beckman pH meter with glass calomel electrode assembly was used for pH measurements. The following mixtures were prepared for each metal and titrated against standard alkali using Bjerrum-Calvin pH-titration technique:

- (a) 5 ml KNO₃ (1.0 M) + 10 ml HNO₃ (0.01 M),

- (b) 5 ml KNO₃ (1.0 M) + 10 ml HNO₃ (0.01 M) + 10 ml ligand (0.01 M),

- (c) 5 ml KNO₃ (1.0 M) + 10 ml HNO₃ (0.01 M) + 10 ml ligand (0.01 M) + 2 ml metal nitrate (0.01 M).

Total volume of each system was kept at 50 ml by appropriate addition of water and dioxan. Representative potentiometric titration curves are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titration curves. A: Free acid; B: Ligand (L); C: Cu(II)-L; D: Ni(II)-L; E: Co(II)-L; F: Fe(III)-L; G: Th(IV)-L.

Protonation constant: The average number of protons associated with a ligand, $\bar{n}_A$, was calculated using the formula of Irving and Rossotti⁵

* Author for correspondence.

$$\bar{n}_A = Y + \frac{(V_1 - V_2)(N^0 + E^0)}{(V_0 + V_1) T_L^0}$$

where V_1 and V_2 denote the volume of alkali required to reach the same pH in titrations of HNO_3 and ligand, respectively, T_L^0 the total concentration of ligand, Y the total number of dissociable protons attached to a ligand, N^0 the normality of alkali, V_0 total volume of mixture and E^0 the initial concentration of free acid. Proton ligand formation curve, obtained by plotting $\bar{n}_A$ values against pH values, was utilized to evaluate the protonation constant employing various computational methods⁴.

Metal-ligand stability constants: The average number of ligand associated with a metal ion, $\bar{n}$, and the free ligand exponent, pL , were calculated by using equations,

$$\bar{n} = \frac{(V_2 - V_1)(N^0 + E^0)}{(V_0 + V_1) \bar{n}_A T_M^0}$$

and

$$pL = \log_{10} \left[\frac{\beta \left(\frac{1}{\text{Antilog } \beta} \right)^n \cdot (V_0 + V_2)}{T_L^0 - \bar{n} T_M^0} \cdot \frac{(V_0 + V_2)}{V_0} \right]$$

Metal ligand formation curves (Fig. 2) obtained by plotting $\bar{n}$ against pL were utilized to calculate successive stability constants of metal complexes using Rossotti's computational techniques⁵.

Fig. 2. Metal ligand formation curves. A: Fe(III)-L; B: Co(II)-L; C: Ni(II)-L; D: Cu(II)-L; E: Zn(II)-L; F: Zr(IV)-L; G: La(III)-L; H: Th(IV)-L.

General method of isolation of complexes: Equimolar amounts of salicylanilide and nickel or cupric nitrate were dissolved in ethanol separately. The solution of salicylanilide was neutralized with equimolar solution of NaOH in ethanol and added to excess of metal nitrate solution with constant stirring. The precipitate was filtered, washed with hot benzene and dried. The Fe(III) complex was isolated by adding neutral solution of salicylanilide into excess ferric chloride solution in ethanol. The mixture was filtered and the filtrate was evaporated.

Residue was recrystallized from ethanol to give Fe(III) complex. Some analytical data of these complexes are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—SOME ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE METAL COMPLEXES OF SALICYLANILIDE

Complex	Colour	% Found (Calcd.)			
		C	H	N	M
Fe[C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ N] ₃	Violet	67.50 (67.30)	4.23 (4.33)	6.57 (6.69)	7.96 (8.09)
Ni[C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ N] ₂	Green	64.27 (64.40)	4.02 (4.14)	5.71 (5.80)	12.28 (12.16)
Cu[C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ N] ₂	Olive green	63.89 (64.0)	4.0 (4.10)	5.62 (5.74)	13.09 (13.02)

Results and Discussion

Protonation constant (Table 2) of salicylanilide was obtained by plotting $\bar{n}_A$ against corresponding pH values and interpolating at half $\bar{n}_A$ value of the curve. Examination of representative titration

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE COMPLEXES OF SOME METAL IONS WITH SALICYLANILIDE; $\mu = 0.1 M (KNO_3)$; $t = 25^\circ$ (PROTONATION CONSTANT OF SALICYLANILIDE, $pK_a = 9.68$)

Metal Ion	$\log k_1$	$\log k_2$	$\log k_3$	$\log \beta$
Fe(III)	9.84	9.76	—	19.60
Co(II)	7.80	7.15	—	14.95
Ni(II)	7.70	7.58	—	15.28
Cu(II)	8.08	7.56	—	15.64
Zn(II)	6.78	5.84	—	12.62
Zr(IV)	8.50	7.58	5.30	21.38
La(III)	7.40	6.28	5.60	19.28
Th(IV)	9.00	8.20	6.65	23.85

curves (Fig. 1) shows that metal titration curves are well separated from the ligand titration curve. Metal-ligand formation curves for Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) (Fig. 2, curves B, C, D and E, respectively) are complete at both ends. Hence values of $\log k_1$ and $\log k_2$ were obtained directly by interpolating at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and 1.5 , respectively. Due to symmetry of formation curves, it was also possible to determine the stability constant data by 'mid point' method. Formation curves of Fe(III), Zr(IV), La(III) and Th(IV) (Fig. 2, curves A, F, G and H, respectively) are, however, incomplete in lower half portions and thus the values of $\log k_2$ and $\log k_3$ were obtained at $\bar{n} = 1.5$ and 2.5 , respectively, while those of $\log k_1$ were obtained using the equation,

$$\log k_1 \cdot k_2 = 2pL \text{ (at } \bar{n} = 1.0)$$

The calculated values of $\log k_1$, $\log k_2$ and $\log k_3$, alongwith the protonation constant (pK_a) of salicylanilide have been reported in Table 2. The $\log k_4$ values for Zr(IV) and Th(IV) could not be calculated due to limited accuracy of $\bar{n}$ values. The general order of overall stability constant values have been found to be: Th(IV) > Zr(IV) > Fe(III) > La(III) > Cu(II) > Ni(II) > Co(II) > Zn(II) in which Fe(III), Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) are according to Irving-Williams' sequence⁶.

In the absence of metal ion hydrolysis, proton release on complexation can be only from the ligand. If the solutions are not highly alkaline, the protonation equilibrium investigated is $HL \rightleftharpoons H^+ + L^-$ and complex formation takes place through the displacement of phenolic hydrogen.

The analysis of representative species distribution curves of Cu(II) complex (Fig. 3) reveals that the concentration of species CuL^+ increases rapidly, attains a limiting value ($\approx 50\%$) at a pH of 5 and decreases beyond this pH, thereby increasing the concentration of CuL_2 . It has been noted that at higher pH values, almost all Cu(II) complexes with salicylanilide in the form of CuL_2 ($\approx 100\%$). Similar observations have been obtained with systems of salicylanilide with other metal ions where substantial decrease in the concentrations of ML^+ species increases the concentrations of ML_2 species. The maximum concentrations of ML^+ type of complexes for Co(II), Ni(II), Zn(II), Zr(IV), La(III) and Th(IV), were found to be 44, 48, 59, 58, 64 and 54%, respectively, whereas for ML_2 type complexes were found to be 95, 95, 96, 87, 50 and 73%, respectively. The concentrations of ML_2 type complexes of Zr(IV), La(III) and Th(IV) were observed to attain limiting values at 93, 95 and 92%, respectively. In all the cases, the concentration of each species tends to approach a limiting value and total concentration of metal, present in various species, was found to be nearly 100% at any pH.

Fig. 3. Species distribution curves [given as the percentage of total Cu(II) present] of several species present in binary system of Cu(II) and salicylanilide ($C_M = 1 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $C_L = 2 \times 10^{-3} M$).

Nature of reaction leading to complex formation: There are three possible binding sites in salicylanilide, two in amide group (one through its oxygen and the other through the nitrogen atom) and the third one through the phenolate oxygen. The negative shift observed in the N-H stretching frequency of ligand from 3270 cm^{-1} to $3250, 3255$ and 3260 cm^{-1} for Fe(III), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes, respectively, has been interpreted as due to intramolecular hydrogen bonding between N-H group and phenolate oxygen bonded to metal

ion and not due to bonding with metal ion as the potentiometric determination of dissociation constant of salicylanilide has provided only one protonation constant (Table 2) due to phenolic group. Further, lowering of $\nu C=O$ of salicylanilide from 1670 cm^{-1} to $1600, 1600$ and 1585 cm^{-1} for Fe(III), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes, respectively, provides substantial evidence that the metal ions are coordinated through oxygen atom of amide group (Structure 1). These results are further supported from the work of Rao⁷, Bilger and Pechmeze⁸ and Pannu and Chopra⁹ on similar systems.

Structure-1

On the basis of present investigation, it has been observed that salicylanilide is capable of forming stable complexes with the metal ions which are found in conjugation with the enzymes where these metal ions may establish 'some sort of equilibrium' with fungicides. Thus, the growth inhibition of fungi may be due to removal of a metal ion from the enzyme to form its complex with fungicide, thereby disturbing the biological activity. Similar observation on dithiocarbamates has been recorded by Gokosyr¹⁰, Smale¹¹ and Kaars Sijpesteijn *et al*¹². A detailed investigation of this mechanism is in progress.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Dr. J. B. Singh (G. S. V. M. Medical College, Kanpur) for experimental facility and Prof. P. R. Singh (I. I. T., Kanpur) for encouragement.

References

1. "Metal Ions in Biological Systems", (Ed.) H. SIGEL, Marcel Dekker, N. Y., 1973.
2. C. H. KAUFFMANN, *Proc. Internat. Congr. Pl. Sci.*, 1929, 2, 1603.
3. M. M. ISHAK and A. A. SARAF, *Com. Gen. Pharmacol.*, 1970, 1, 201.
4. M. KOFLAY, C. K. R. KURKUR, K. W. LAM and D. R. SANDI, *Biochem.*, 1970, 9, 3599.
5. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397; 1954, 2904.
6. H. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *Nature*, 1948, 162, 746.
7. C. N. R. RAO, "Chemical Application of Infrared Spectroscopy", Academic Press, London, 1963.
8. X. BILGER and J. PECHMEZE, *Chem. Abs.*, 1959, 53, 15097c.
9. B. S. PANNU and S. L. CHOPRA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 732.
10. J. GOKOSYR, *Physiol. Pantarum*, 1955, 8, 719.
11. B. C. SMALE, *Dissertation Abs.*, 1958, 18, 374.
12. A. KAARS SIJPESTEIJN, M. J. JANSSENA and G. J. M. VANDERKERK, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta*, 1957, 23, 550.